

See What You Feel: Visualizing Static Haptic Scenes

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Abstract. Novices to haptic design may struggle to predict how different force-feedback effects would combine across the workspace of their device. While haptic simulations often include a visual component, these graphics frequently rely on metaphor. For example, while a graphical display of a piece of wood may be used to indicate that a surface should feel similar to wood, this would not necessarily reflect the actual force-feedback effects one would experience when interacting with the simulated material. As more haptic elements and interactions are included, a novice would need to feel the resulting forces sequentially and may be surprised when these results clash with expectations formed from the metaphorical view. We aim to develop visualizations of haptic properties from two-dimensional scenes to help novices develop an intuition for how the components of their designs interact. We present our current approaches and discuss planned work to integrate our method into beginner-friendly development environments so that visualizations are easily accessible.

Keywords: Education · force feedback · visualization

1 Introduction

A growing number of novice hapticians will need to learn to design haptic experiences as hardware becomes more affordable. This paper focuses on helping these individuals develop an intuition for haptic effects, and debug issues in their creations, by visualizing the haptic properties of force fields, textures, and friction characteristics of the scene. Although the sensation of force-feedback cannot be replaced, it is time consuming to comb the entire workspace to ensure expected outputs. By visualizing these forces in an easy-to-understand manner, a haptic designer can quickly gauge the effects within the scene without having to experience them. We propose that these visualizations would be a useful addition to introductory haptic design and development environments.³

³ e.g., <https://gitlab.com/Haply/2diy/learn>.

Visualizations of force-feedback haptic effects are primarily developed as part of haptic authoring tools. For example, van Oosterhout et al. represented effects for a 1 degree-of-freedom (DoF) device as waveforms with force as a function of position or time [4]. However, such an approach does not easily extend to 2- or 3-DoF devices. Three-dimensional visuals, such as those in game engines, have been used to apply haptic elements within a 3D environment [1,2], but offer little to visually indicate how an effect will feel or interact with other elements.

Our work aims to provide an “at a glance” representation of force-feedback scenes across more than one spatial dimension. For simplicity, we focus on linear time-invariant scenes for a 2-DoF device where the haptic elements simulated within the scene cannot move.

2 Prototype Design

In 2D scenes consisting solely of static elements, the force f exerted on the end effector is a function of its position $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$, its velocity $\dot{x} = \frac{dx}{dt}$, and time $t \geq 0$. We decompose force f into components using familiar terms such as static, friction, and texture forces to improve learnability for novices. We model all forces that depend solely on position as $f_{static}(x)$, forces that additionally depend on velocity as $f_{friction}(x, \dot{x})$, and all remaining forces that vary over time as $f_{texture}(x, \dot{x}, t)$.

(Figure 1) contains three large springs (two troughs and one hill), three areas of friction overlapping each spring, and two texture surfaces at the top and bottom of the scene.⁴ A study on graduate students with high-school science backgrounds found that field forces were often represented by quiver plots [3]. As such, we represented $f_{static}(x)$ in 2D with a colour map for intensity and quiver plot for direction. Coloured contours were used to indicate regions with varying coefficients of friction, while grids of points with varying transparency and density were used to evoke areas with different $f_{texture}(x)$, components. Since this approach relies heavily on colour, a 3D version was created where static forces are instead represented by changes in elevation, another representation favoured by participants in Reiner’s study [3]. This change allowed surface colouring, not just contour colouring, to represent friction. A texture-specific view remains to be implemented so viewers can anticipate with more detail how textures differ.

3 Conclusion and Future Work

With the goal of supporting haptic design learning, we propose two approaches to visualizing a subset of 2-DoF force-feedback scenes. We plan to improve these visualization methods through user testing and to assess different concepts, for example, providing a frequency-domain representation of texture forces.

Since separately specifying the static, friction, and texture forces poses a barrier to novices engaged in active development, future work includes adding

⁴ Code, 2D/3D examples: <https://github.com/emmanuelwilson/VisualizingHaptics>

Fig. 1: 2D and 3D representations of the same scene generated by our algorithm. A and G represent spring forces, using a 2D colour-map and a quiver plot while 3D uses hill/valley surface deformations. B and H show destructive superposition of two springs (pull + pull). C. Constructive superposition of two springs (obstructed in 3D). D and I represent friction forces, resistive forces found inside the contour plots in 2D or a colour-map of friction values in 3D. E and J is an area of friction overlap. F and K are texture based forces as a scatter plot. Point density and opacity are proportional to frequency and amplitude respectively.

functionality to generate these visualizations directly from prototypes under development. We hope that providing these improved visualizations will result in accelerating student learning of the basics for force-feedback development.

Acknowledgments. This work was funded by Healthy Brains, Healthy Lives. The second author is supported by NSERC (569236) and FRQNT (315050) scholarships.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare.

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